

EMOTIONAL PROFILING

“

did you know?

The brain's engagement with audio is transferred to the ads [...] According to our research with Neuro-Insight, **Spotify audio ads saw 19% higher Brand Impact** compared to all other media.

”

AND MARKETING ON SPOTIFY

EMOTIONAL PROFILING

“

did you know?

There's no doubt [...] millennials are passionate about music!

Three in four millennials say music is part of how they define who they are.

”

AND MARKETING ON SPOTIFY

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did you know?

As the #1 music platform for
music discovery and
recommendations among
millennials,
**Spotify is at the centre of their
lives**

”

AND MARKETING ON SPOTIFY

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did you know?

Unlike generations past, millennials aren't loyal to any specific music genre. Instead, **they pride themselves on being open-minded** [...] with 84% stating that their music tastes span multiple genres.

”

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did you know?

74% of you believe in gender fluidity, one-third juggle several different careers simultaneously, and **64% believe that labeling people unnecessarily divides them.**

”

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did you know?

While **millennials' resistance to defining themselves by geography, sexuality, career choice and music genre has made marketing a challenge**, this shift to always-on audio streaming also presents new opportunities to get your message heard through personalised experiences that match the mood and occasion.

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did you know?

Millennials represent the largest and most diverse audience in history, this throws a wrench in marketers' neat audience segmentations.

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did you know?

Spotify has identified seven key audio streaming moments to tap into, as well as recommendations on how to use our **streaming intelligence on millennials' moods, mindsets, tastes and habits** to build effective creative strategies and media plans.

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did you know?

Spotify creates a space for people to listen, learn, and connect. The music and conversations people have access to on our platform help **shape listeners' identities, cultures, and communities.**

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did you know?

Because the listening experience is intimate and personal, **it's important to create audio that reflects your brand's commitment to your audience**—and the culture they're part of or tuning into.

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did you know?

Gen Z's discover and connect to
culture through streaming.

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did you know?

Two-thirds (62%) of gen Z's believe that **streaming platforms** at large have significantly **shaped how they discover and connect with the broader culture.**

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did you know?

Marketing 101: You should **lead with a story**. You spark a connection and send listeners on a journey when you tell a story.

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did you know?

Marketing 101: Utilize narrative that helps us understand others' perspectives: When you listen to a story of someone else's life, it's as if you're living their story for those brief moments. That experience allows you to learn from other people's experiences.

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did you know?

Marketing 101:

Transport listeners from their own realities to the worlds we imagine.

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did you know?

Marketing 101:
Spark a connection. Craft a story
that's going to resonate and relate.

”

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did you know?

Marketing 101:

Be conscientious. Consider **using narratives that are relevant** and conscious of current social climates.

”

AND MARKETING ON SPOTIFY

PROMPTS

the challenge

**You may follow a basic
story map.**

Introduce the setting, create the main character (and possibly a secondary one), develop a plot (something significant happens), and conclude with an outcome.

FICTIONAL SPOTIFY USER

PROMPTS

the challenge

**Streaming services, like
Spotify, become illegal...**

FICTIONAL SPOTIFY USER

PROMPTS

the challenge

**Satan puts you in charge
of hell, and you need to
create the worst user
experience for listening to
music...**

FICTIONAL SPOTIFY USER

PROMPTS

the challenge

**Consider your day from
the perspective of your
fictional characters...**

FICTIONAL SPOTIFY USER

PROMPTS

the challenge

**While browsing the
supermarket aisles,
someone approaches you
and says, “I need you to
listen to me very carefully;
this is of the utmost
concern. It is about your
music choices...”**

FICTIONAL SPOTIFY USER

1

**What “things” do
we want choice or
control over?**

BASIC INQUIRIES

2

**What tactics might
enable choice or
control over those
“things”?**

BASIC INQUIRIES

3

How to prototype those tactics?

BASIC INQUIRIES

SHAPING

**What aspects does the
algorithmic system aim to
detect about your emotional
state? Can it “say” anything
about your emotional state?**

YOUR EMOTIONAL STATE

SHAPING

Can it influence or alter your emotional state, such as transitioning from sadness to happiness or maintaining your current state?

YOUR EMOTIONAL STATE

SHAPING

**Where would you prefer your
emotional state to transition?**

Would you be ok with this?

YOUR EMOTIONAL STATE

SHAPING

When considering emotional nuances, like a breakup versus general despair, what specific emotional outcomes do you desire? For instance, preferring rage over happiness for a certain affective shaping.

YOUR EMOTIONAL STATE

SHAPING

**Should the algorithm
optimize for happiness as the
desired emotional state?**

YOUR EMOTIONAL STATE

SHAPING

How would these transitions differ when focusing on individual versus collective stances? For instance, during a party's "start a jam" session, what insights can be gleaned about the group's collective emotional state?

YOUR EMOTIONAL STATE